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<p style="text-align: center;">身地相涵作為臺灣選物販賣機（夾娃娃機）產業文化邁向地方學的文化論述</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Mutual Inclusiveness of Body and Place (MIBP) as Cultural Discussion Moving towards Locality for UFO Catcher (Claw Machine) Industrial Culture in Taiwan</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Yu-Yang Chen</p> <p style="text-align: center;">College of Science, National Taipei University of Education</p> <p style="text-align: center;">摘要 / Abstract</p> <p>The UFO Catcher (Claw Machine) industry culture in Taiwan has been developed for more than 30 years. After many changes in the social, political, and economic environments, the core structure exists by the trinity of “Suppliers-Machine-hosts (and storefront owner)-Clients” nowadays. As a foreign industrial culture that has not yet been rooted in Taiwan, the UFO Catcher industrial culture is often regarded as an existence that has nothing to do with “locality”. However, this industrial culture is extremely popular in Taiwan, and has been closely linked with ordinary life of people. To have a more in-depth and extensive exploration of this industrial culture in Taiwan in the future, this research analyzes the industrial culture of UFO Catcher through the concept of “Mutual Inclusiveness of Body and Place” (MIBP), making it a step towards the cultural discourse of the Locality of Taiwan. The MIBP focuses on the “body-place” relationship and points out the importance of experience sense for the mutual inclusion and referential relationship between “body/corporeality” and “place/sense of place”. The physical senses and the sense of place are connected in series, and mutual acculturation is formed to form an interpenetrating appearance. Among them, the “bodying place” and the “localized body” serve as the eyes of cultural perspective. Combining the interaction of this industrial and cultural structure with regional investigation, the characteristics of construct, infiltrating, alienation and intersectionality between body and place are revealed. The core structure of the UFO Catcher cultural industry takes “people” as the subject and the actors, the individual's physical sense of self depends on interaction with each other. The local characteristics of the distribution area of this cultural industry show that its existence depends on the sensitivity to the locality. The concept of MIBP as an approach to the construction of the vending machine industry culture and connecting it with the local area is the foundation for the future discourse on locality of Taiwan.</p>			
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